

A P O L L O

D7.6: Dissemination Pack

WP7 – Exploitation and Communication

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the APOLLO Dissemination Pack: a collection of communication, dissemination and marketing material to promote greater awareness of the project.

The Dissemination Pack is comprised of:

- The APOLLO Brochure
- The APOLLO Leaflet
- The APOLLO Website
- The APOLLO Newsletter
- The APOLLO Fact Sheets
- The APOLLO Press Kit

The brochure and website are available in their first versions (the brochure is undergoing finalisation based on comments received from partners). The newsletter is operational and the first edition has been delivered. In agreement with the project coordinator, the fact sheets have been postponed due to the current maturity level of the technical solution. The leaflet is still in production but is expected to be delivered within the next month. The full press kit will be made available upon the completion of the full set of documents, in the meanwhile, a partial press kit will be delivered to journalists.

1 Introduction

This deliverable introduces the items comprising the APOLLO Dissemination Pack. The APOLLO Dissemination Pack is comprised of:

- The APOLLO Brochure
- The APOLLO Leaflet
- The APOLLO Website
- The APOLLO Newsletter
- The APOLLO Fact Sheets
- The APOLLO Press Kit

Each of these communication products is described in the sections below along with screenshots.

2 Brochure

The APOLLO Brochure is an 8-page, A4 portrait, glossy communication product. It provides a detailed overview of the benefits and advantages of the APOLLO service with a view to creating brand awareness and attracting new customers. It is intended for distribution in print and via the web to farmers, farmers' associations, agricultural consultants, the research community and the general public.

The brochure is currently in the final stages of lay-out, with minor changes pending to some of the iconography, including the final decision on the front cover. The images which follow display the various spreads comprising the brochure.

Figure 1: APOLLO Brochure – Spread 1 - Front and back covers

Figure 2: APOLLO Brochure – Spread 2 - Pages 1 and 2

Figure 3: APOLLO Brochure – Spread 3 - Pages 3 and 4

Figure 4: APOLLO Brochure – Spread 4 - Pages 4 and 5

3 Leaflet

The APOLLO Leaflet will be an A4 landscape, matte communication product, to be folded into a triptych (outside thirds folded inwards) in its printed form. The purpose of the leaflet is attracting the attention of target audiences with a small number of key messages, triggering brand awareness and encouraging visitors to the website. It is intended for distribution in print and via the web to farmers, farmers' associations, agricultural consultants, the policy and research communities and the general public.

The content of the leaflet will be a highly summarised version of certain key sections within the brochure. It will emphasise some of the main messages of the APOLLO narrative, such as:

- The main strapline: “APOLLO services are affordable, accessible and easy-to-use”
- “Any time or place, for many crops on multiple devices - APOLLO services are readily accessible”.
- “Built for farmers, by farmers: APOLLO is designed with the help of real farmers to make it user-friendly and easy to navigate.”

The leaflet is still in production but is expected to be delivered within the next month.

4 Website

The APOLLO website (www.apollo-h2020.eu) serves as the online marketing tool of the project. Its key purpose is raising awareness of the project's goals, activities and results and promoting the APOLLO platform to the main target audience: farmers, farmers' associations and agricultural consultants. It provides key information about the project and the future commercial services, in a concise and appealing manner, including:

- Description of project objectives, partners and funding;
- Public deliverable documents, results and latest news;
- Announcements on project activities and involvement opportunities;
- Promotional materials.

The APOLLO website was first released for comment on 28 August 2016, and formally made public in September 2016 (M05). In its first version, the website is focused on communicating the **project-related** aspects of APOLLO, whilst the second release (M12) will focus on promoting the commercial services.

Several snapshots of the website's homepage are available in the figures below.

Figure 5: APOLLO Website – Homepage – 1

Figure 6: APOLLO Website – Homepage – 2

Figure 7: APOLLO Website – Homepage – 3

Figure 8: APOLLO Website – Homepage - 4

5 Newsletter

The APOLLO project publishes a **regular, trimonthly newsletter** to inform subscribers of upcoming events, project milestones, and relevant news stories linked to the broader fields of precision agriculture and smart farming. The main purpose of the newsletter is to announce project-related events, communicate project news, and maintain the interest and awareness of subscribers as the project progresses.

The newsletter was designed, and is distributed, using the online service MailChimp. The first APOLLO Newsletter was released in October 2016.

A snapshot of the first issue of the newsletter is presented in the image below.

Figure 9: APOLLO Newsletter – Issue 1 - Excerpt

6 Fact Sheets

A set of fact sheets is planned as part of the communication toolkit of the APOLLO project. The purpose of the fact sheet is to summarising key information on the four services offered by APOLLO: Soil workability, irrigation scheduling, crop growth monitoring and crop yield estimation.

Due to the current maturity level of the project, the fact sheets will be delivered at or before M12, coinciding with the release of the pre-operational services.

7 Press Kit

The APOLLO Press Kit will be a collection of published materials on the APOLLO project, including:

- The set of 4 APOLLO fact sheets
- The APOLLO Brochure
- The APOLLO Leaflet
- The most recent APOLLO Press Release
- An information sheet containing:
 - Links to the project's website and social media accounts
 - A synthetic summary of the project
 - Key points and messages to be highlighted in a published article
 - Links to the previous press releases of the project

The full press kit will be made available upon the completion of the leaflet and the fact sheets. In the meanwhile, a partial press kit, containing the rest of the items listed above, will be delivered.

The first Press Release of the project is included in the image below.

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PRESS RELEASE

The APOLLO EU project sets out to bring affordable precision agriculture to smallholder farmers

FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE

Brussels, Belgium, 5th July 2016

APOLLO is an EU project aiming to develop agricultural advisory services aimed primarily, but not exclusively, at smallholder farmers. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to farmers through affordable information services, making extensive use of free and open Earth Observation data, such as those provided by the EU's Copernicus programme. These services will help farmers to make better decisions by monitoring the growth and health of crops, providing advice on when to irrigate and till their fields and estimating the size of their harvest. Ultimately, these interventions should lead to less waste and higher yields - and therefore increased profitability and competitiveness.

The APOLLO project brings together nine partners from five European countries (Greece, Spain, Austria, Belgium and Serbia), and combines expertise in agronomy, agricultural services, soil science, remote sensing and Earth Observation. The consortium is proud to include two farmers' associations – the Agricultural Cooperative of Pella in Greece, and the Association of Farmers of the Municipality of Ruma in Serbia, who will pilot and test early versions of the services. A third pilot will be carried out in Spain.

APOLLO responds to a series of challenges facing the agricultural sector as a whole, and smallholder farmers in particular. Global population growth means that farmers will need to grow twice as much as they do today in order to feed the planet's 9 billion inhabitants¹. At the same time, there is less land available for agricultural production, thanks to the expanding population, soil erosion and water scarcity. Finally, there are social and regulatory pressures on farmers to reduce their environmental impact: in other words, to use less pesticides, fertiliser, water and fuel.

Precision agriculture can help to address these challenges. Detailed information about the state and health of crops allows farmers to apply chemicals and water in the precise quantities required, where and when they are needed. This approach is extensively used by large-scale farm managers, but is still relatively new to small-scale farmers, who often cannot afford heavy investments in new technologies. APOLLO aims to open up the precision agriculture market by making affordable and easy-to-use agricultural advisory services available to farmers, farmer associations and agricultural consultants.

The APOLLO project was successfully launched at its inaugural meeting, held in Thessaloniki on the 12th and 13th of May 2016. The pace and output of the meeting reflected the complementarity of the partners and the strength of the several working relationships which already exist between many of them. The discussions converged on issues such as the nature and variety of the target users in the different countries, how best to approach the collection of user requirements, and the technical issues to be overcome in developing the services. A special visitor to the kick-off meeting was a Serbian farmer, invited by the Ruma farmers' association, who shared his views on the opportunities and challenges of introducing new technological solutions to smallholder farmers.

¹ <http://www.worldwildlife.org/stories/freezing-the-footprint-of-food>

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Figure 10: APOLLO Press Release – Project Launch – Page 1

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PRESS RELEASE

Since its launch, the project has been represented at several geospatial and space-related events: the Geospatial World Forum, the European Space Solutions conference, the NEREUS event "What can Sentinels do for regions?" and the Copernicus Agriculture and Forestry Applications User Requirements Workshop.

Preparations are now underway for the collection of user requirements for the APOLLO services through a survey and focus groups. The project team invites interested parties (farmers, agricultural consultants, associations) to get in touch in order to express their views, participate in the survey, and subscribe to the project's mailing list.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Figure 11: APOLLO Press Release – Project Launch – Page 2

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8 Conclusion

The APOLLO Dissemination Pack is a collection of documents aimed at enabling the promotion and awareness-raising of the project through print and digital media.

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